

Impact of Mind and Concept Mappings Strategies on Map Reading Skills Among Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the Impact of Mind and Concept Mappings Strategies on Map Reading Skills Among Senior Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria. Two research objectives, research questions and corresponding null hypotheses. The research design adopted for the study was pretest posttest control group quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study consisted of 6623 (Male, 3765 and Female, 2858) Senior Secondary School class two SSII geography students from twenty one schools in during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. Three co-educational public senior secondary schools were selected using Clustered sampling technique. A total number of 183 (Male, 78 and Female, 105) Senior Secondary School class two students formed the sample of the study. Using an intact classes. Geography Skills Acquisition Scale (GSAS) were developed and used in data collection. The GSAS was validated by experts and reliability coefficient of 0.601 was obtained. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics, while the null hypothesis were tested using ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean scores of skills acquisitions of geography students taught map reading concept using Mind Mapping, Concept Mapping and those exposed to lecture method. It was concluded that the use Mind Mapping, Concept Mapping strategies is effective in enhancing students' skills acquisition in geography. Based on the research findings it was recommended, State Ministry of education should provide adequate seminars, workshops and training, re-training of teachers to adopt mind and concept mappings teaching strategies for effective teaching and learning of geography in secondary schools.

Keywords: Map Reading Skills, Mind Mapping Strategies, Concept Mapping Strategies and Students

Introduction

Geography as a school subject is one of the most important subjects in secondary school education. Geography is relevant for both the students who are likely to continue to tertiary level and those who will not proceed. It equips students with a body of knowledge to make them functional and socially relevant in the fast-changing world. Geography is a distinct and dynamic science and or social science discipline that deals with the study of man and his physical environment (Ibrahim & Salisu 2023).

According to Ibrahim and Salisu (2023) It is the field that concerned with sharing the scientific content, process skills and developing efficient teaching methods affect achievement in science education. Teaching science may require special attention and efficacy of teachers in order to better attract students and teach the subjects through concrete and clear methods, through the use of individual problem-solving skills. The strategies adopted for teaching Geography include; field trip, discovery method, models, games and simulations, observation and practical work.

Map reading is the process of looking at the map to determine what is depicted and how the cartographer depicted it. This involves identifying the features or phenomena depicted, the symbols and labels used, and information about the map that may not be evident on the map (Ibrahim & Salisu 2023).

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Mind mapping is defined as an interesting note-taking style that describes what you think (Ibrahim, 2023). Broadly speaking, mind mapping actively involves both of our brains and can help us to think creatively. In the other hand, concept mapping used as a learning and teaching technique visually illustrates the relationship between concepts and ideas, often represented in circles or boxes, concept are linked by words and phrases that explain the connection better the ideas, helping students organize and structure the thoughts to further understand information and discover new relationship (Ibrahim & Salisu 2023).

Statement of the Research Problem

One of the problems of teaching Geography identified by Liman, Babajo and Hari (2022) is the persistent failure in senior secondary school's certificate examination (SSCE) among students. Ibrahim (2020) reported that factors identified as a bane of poor student's performance in geography is the use of faulty and inappropriate teaching method like lecture method. According to Salisu (2019) stated that due to its nature, common use of teacher-centered method to teaching leads to poor understanding, assimilation and application of learning, while the use of student-centered methods enhances students' achievement, thus, the need to find out whether Mind and concept mapping are learner-centered teaching/learning method, would enhance student's performance in geography.

However, the use of different approaches and techniques in which the students' ability to utilizes their skills should be encouraged. Therefore, teachers must act as the catalysts of the students in teaching geographical concepts, such as map reading. This enables students to assume full responsibility about the organization of their work. Skills include: observation, interpretation of data, measurements, and classification of data (Ibrahim 2023). Skilled enough to use map, students show a greater motivation to learn within this environment and a greater predisposition to use maps. Teachers who adopt strategies of enhancing students' skills might be regarded as predictors of development, proper utilization of skills could help the students to provide feedback and also improves their performance throughout the teaching process (Ibrahim 2023).

The purpose of secondary science education is to equip young learners with scientific process skills, to enable them to define existing problems, observe events in their society, analyze and hypothesize possible solutions, conclude and generalize and apply gathered information for the betterment and advancement of his community (Ibrahim 2023).

According to Mbewe, Chabalengula, and Mumba (2010) and Huppert, Lomask, and Lazarowitz (2002) cited in Derilo (2019) reiterated that the Science Process Skill acquisition is the main objective of science education because of the fact that science process skills is needed by every individual in whole citizenry, and not just the scientific community. Huppert and colleagues further pointed out that since Skills acquisition are applicable to all elements of the community, everyone should be knowledgeable on how it could be applied in everyday living.

To overcome the problem, scholars advocate the use of innovative strategies like Mind-mapping. Ayca Kartal, Kaya Tuncer, Cennet and Ozlem Ozcakil (2015) has taking the views of teacher candidates on the implementation of the mind-mapping technique on Geography courses and at under-graduate level, is thought to be an important step to contribute to increase the applicability of the technique. Against this background the study is set to examine the Impact of Mind and Concept Mapping Techniques on Map Reading Skills Among Senior Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study is to:

1. investigate the effects of Mind and Concept Mappings on Map Reading skills among senior secondary school Students in Katsina State.

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Research Questions

The following research question were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping strategies and those taught the same concept using lecture method in Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

The following Null Hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping and those taught the same concept using lecture method in Katsina State.

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi experimental research design, specifically, pre-test post-test control group design;

Table 1: Design

Group	Description
EG ₁	Experimental Group 1
EG ₂	Experimental Group 2
X ₁	Treatment (Teaching using Mind Mapping)
X ₂	Treatment (Teaching using Concept mapping)
X ₀	No Treatment (Teaching with lecture method)
O ₁	Pre-test
O ₂	Post-test

Pre-test (O₁) were administered to both experimental and control group to ensure careful selection of samples that are not significantly different in terms of skills acquisition and academic performance before treatment, in other word to establish equivalence of the groups before treatment. Subject were assigned to experimental and control prior to the administration of treatment. The three groups were taught Map Reading concept for a period of six weeks. Post-test (O₂) were then be administered after treatment to determine impact of instructional methods on students' skills acquisition, interest and academic performance.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consist of all Government Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) Geography students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina State, Nigeria. The schools consisted of all of public schools that offer Geography within the metropolis. There are 25 public schools out of which 21 schools are offering geography with population of 6,623. The number of male students was 3,765 and female students 2,858 making a total population of 6,623.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample of the study covered a total number of 183 SS II geography students from three coeducational schools in the study area. The choice of 183 students as a sample is in line with the recommendation of Tucker (1973), Kerlinger (1989), Sambo (2008), Salisu (2022) and central limit theorem that recommend for a number of 30 participants as viable enough to form a study sample in an experimental research. In order to ensure selection of subject with comparative abilities, the researcher analyzed the result of pre-test administered to 12 out of 21 secondary schools, using Analysis of variance.

The outcome revealed significant difference, the researcher used Schiffer's Post-hoc test to determine the direction of disparity. As a result, six schools revealed no significance difference. In order to select the schools, Cluster sampling was used from which three schools were randomly selected from the number of schools in the area of this study through balloting. The researcher wrote the names of all the 21 public secondary schools on pieces of papers and randomly selected three schools.

Sampled Schools

Table 2. Sample Distribution of the Students

S/N	School	Status	Male	Female	Total
1	School A	Experimental (E1)	24	39	63
2	School B	Experimental (E2)	27	26	53
3	School C	Control	27	40	67
	Total		78	105	183

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Instrumentation

In this study two research instruments namely Geography Skills Acquisition scale (GSAS) were used for data collection. It was an instrument adapted from Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (2007), and were used in determining the skills acquisition of Geography students in Map Reading concepts. The original instrument contained more than five hundred items from different field of sciences such as Geography, Chemistry, Physics, Agricultural science, Biology and Mathematics using different scale such as Likert five points scale. The scale contained twenty (20) items in which the first five 5 items measure observation skills, the second 5 items measure classification skills, the third 5 items measure the measurement skills and the last 5 items measure inferring skills. The scale was selected because it has been used widely in the literature in order to assess skills acquisition characteristics.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping strategies and those taught the same concept using lecture method in Katsina State?

Table 3: Means and Standard Deviations of skills acquisition scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Grouping	N	Mean	SD	SE	M Diff
Mind Mapping	63	58.90	8.09	1.02	
Concept mapping	53	60.24	8.10	1.11	1.34
Lecture Method	67	38.41	11.10	1.35	21.83
Total	183	51.79	13.78	1.01	

Table 4.1 presents Mean and Standard Deviations of skills acquisition scores of Experimental and Control Groups. From the results, geography students taught map reading using mind mapping scored a mean of 58.90 and Standard Deviation of 8.09; students taught using concept mapping scored a mean of 60.24 and Standard Deviation of 8.10, while students taught using lecture method scored a mean of 38.41 and Standard Deviations of 11.10. From the result it is observed that students taught using concept mapping acquired skills higher than those taught using mind mapping followed by those taught using lecture method.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping and those taught the same concept using lecture method.

Table 4. ANOVA of skills acquisition of Experimental and control Groups

Source of Varia.	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Value	P-Value	Remark
Between Groups	18958.571	2	9479.285	109.254	0.01	
Within Groups	15617.538	180	86.764			*Sig
Total	34576.109	182				

Table 4 presents ANOVA of significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping and those taught the same concept using lecture method. From the result, sum of squares between groups is 18958.571, sum of squares within groups is 15617.538. F-Value recorded is 109.254 and p-value obtained is 0.01. The P-Value is less than alpha value of 0.05, hence there is significant difference. Consequently, null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading using mind mapping, concept mapping and those taught the same concept using lecture method is rejected. To determine the direction of disparity, the researcher run post-Hoc test using sheffer and the result is presented in Table 5.

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Table 5. Sheffer Post-Hoc test of Direction of Differences in skills acquisition scores of Experimental and control groups.

(I) Grouping	(J) Grouping	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Remark
Mind Mapping	Concept mapping	-1.34052	1.73616	.743	No Sig.
	Lecture Method	20.48685*	1.63468	.01	*sig.
Concept mapping	Mind Mapping	1.34052	1.73616	.743	No Sig.
	Lecture Method	21.82737*	1.71232	.000	*sig.
Lecture Method	Mind Mapping	-20.48685*	1.63468	.000	*sig.
	Concept mapping	-21.82737*	1.71232	.000	*sig.

Table 5 presents Sheffer Post-Hoc test of Direction of Differences in skills acquisition scores of Experimental and control groups. From the results, p-value of 0.74 was recorded between mind mapping and concept mapping. This means that there is no significant difference between the two methods. However, p-value of 0.01 was recorded between mind mapping and lecture method. This means that there is significant difference in favour of mind mapping.

From the same results, p-value of 0.74 was recorded between concept mapping and mind mapping. This means that there is no significant difference between the two methods. However, p-value of 0.01 was recorded between concept mapping and lecture method. This means that there is significant difference in favour of concept mapping.

Similarly, the results revealed significant difference in favour of mind mapping and concept mapping as p-value of 0.01 was recorded in all the cases.

Discussions

The study investigated the Impact of Mind and Concept Mapping Techniques on Skills Acquisition Among Senior Secondary Geography Students in Katsina State, Nigeria. Finding number, one shows that there was significant difference in the mean skills acquisition scores of geography students taught map reading concept using mind mapping and concept mapping and those exposed to lecture method. This implies that subjects in the experimental group who were exposed to mind mapping and concept mapping developed more skills in map reading concept better than the subjects in the control group who were exposed to lecture method and can be used to improve the skills acquisition of students in map reading techniques of secondary schools' geography curriculum. This finding agrees with several other studies, such as that of Teresa and Carter (2018); Samuel, Libata and Sabitu (2018); Gunawan, Harjono, Hermansyah, and Herayanti (2019); Acarli and Dervisoglu (2021) who conclude that there was a statistically significant difference in the skills acquisition of students when exposed to innovative teaching strategies such as Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping compared to lecture method.

In Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping students form themselves as cooperative groups in which they perceive that they can reach their learning goals if and only other group members also reach their goal. So, it helps the students develop note by themselves and burst critical thinking to students as well as expanding the horizon of the brain hemisphere which are logical thinking and reasoning. The use of Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping removes the barriers associated with teacher centered instructional methods and offers a very unique learning situation in which learners are given opportunities to actively seek for information, analyzed it and construct knowledge by themselves.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, it can be concluded that the use of Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping techniques is effective in enhancing students' skills acquisition and academic performance in geography, in other words employment of Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping strategies have the potential of enhancing academic performance in geography.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The use of Mind Mapping and Concept Mapping improved the map reading skills acquisition ability of students in the present study. As such therefore, teachers and students of geography should be encouraged to use the two strategies as alternative or innovative teaching strategy in order to improve teaching and learning of geography.
2. The government and STAN, ANG, NERDC should inculcate the habit of adopting new teaching strategies that will enable both teachers and students interact and actively involved in the lesson, however, publishers should learn the skills of adopting new strategies such as Mind Mapping into their textbooks. This will enable the students and the reader to develop interest and skills acquisition ability also will improve.

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3. State Ministry of education among others at all levels should provide adequate seminars, workshops and training of teachers to adopt the new teaching strategies for effective classroom delivery.

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